

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, SURATHKAL, MANGALORE-574 146

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled "*Reliable and Effective Health Monitoring System using Advanced Sensors*" is a bonafide work carried out by Mr. Mukesh k, Mr.Santhosh kumar, Ms Supriya k ,Ms Suzanne John Britto bearing the USN's 1SU18CS024, 1SU18CS038 , 1SU18CS044 ,1SU18CS046 in the partial fulfillment for the award of Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science and Engineering of the Srinivas University- Institute of Engineering and Technology during the year 2021-2022. It is certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the department library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

Name & Signature of the Guide & HoD
Mrs. Shifana Begum

Signature of the Dean

Dr. Thomas Pinto
Dean, SUIET, Mukka

External Viva

Name of the Examiners

1.
2. VARSHA G B

Signature with date

01/08/2022

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, SURATHKAL, MANGALORE-574146

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled "**Smart CCTV- AI & ML Based Surveillance System**" is a bonafide work carried out by **Ms. Pooja Naik, Ms. Shannon Raina Periera, Ms. U N Sonalaxmi, Ms. Vaishnavi** bearing the USN **ISU18CS029, ISU18CS040, ISU18CS049, ISU18CS050** in the partial fulfilment for the award of **Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science and Engineering** of the Srinivas University Institute of Engineering and Technology during the year **2021-2022**. It is certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the department library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

29/06/2022

Name & Signature of the Guide

Ms. Swarna H.R

29/6/2022

Name & Signature of the H.O.D

Mrs. Shifana Begum

29/6/22

Signature of the Dean

Dr. Thomas Pinto
Dean, SUIET, Mukka

External Viva

Name of the Examiners

1.

VARSHA G B

Signature with date

29/6/22

01/07/2022

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, MANGALORE-574146

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the internship project entitled "**NOVEL TECHNIQUES TO DETECT BRAIN TUMOR IN MR IMAGE USING SUPERPIXELS, PCA AND TK-MEANS CLUSTERING ALGORITHM**)" is a bonafide work carried out by **Ms.Deeksha B, Ms.Deekshitha H, Ms.Harshitha** bearing the USN **ISU18CS007, ISU18CS008, ISU18CS011** in the partial fulfillment for the award of Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science and Engineering of the Srinivas University-College of Engineering and Technology during the year **2021-2022**. It is certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the department library. The internship report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of internship work prescribed for the said degree.

Name & Signature of the Guide
Mrs. Varsha G B

Name & Signature of the H.O.D
Mrs. Shifana Begum

Signature of the Dean

Dr. Thomas Pinto

Dean, SUCET, Mukka

External Viva

Name of the Examiners

- Nagaraja Hubbal
- VARSHA G B

Signature with date

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING & TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, MANGALURU – 574 146

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled "**Covid-19 and Pneumonia Detection using CNN**" is a bonafide work carried out by *Mohammed Bilal, Nandagopal S, Sushanth S Shetty* bearing the USN *ISU18CS022, ISU18CS025, ISU18CS045* in the partial fulfillment for the award of **Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science and Engineering** of the **Srinivas University, Institute of Engineering & Technology** during the year **2021-22**. It is certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the department library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

Ms. Dyanila Neeta Ferrao.
(Mini Project Guide)

Prof. Shifana Begum.
(Head of the Department)

Signature of the Dean

Dr. Thomas Pinto
Dean, SUIET, Mukka

Name of the Examiners

1. Nagan Hebbal
2. VARSHA G B

Signature with date

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, SURATHKAL, MANGALORE-574146

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled "*Credit Card Fraud Detection using Machine Learning*" is a bonafide work carried out by *Ms. Nidhi Shetty, Ms. Prajna A S, Ms. Simran Samad, Ms. Varsha R Shetty* bearing the *ISU18CS027, ISU18CS031, ISU18CS043, ISU18CS052* in the partial fulfilment for the award of Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science and Engineering of the Srinivas University Institute of Engineering and Technology during the year 2021-2022. It is certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the department library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

Varsha
30/06/2022

Name & Signature of the Guide

Mrs. Varsha G B

Shifana
30/6/2022

Name & Signature of the H.O.D

Mrs. Shifana Begum

Thomas Pinto
30/6/22

Signature of the Dean

Dr. Thomas Pinto
Dean, SUIET, Mukka

External Viva

Name of the Examiners

1. *Nagaraj Hebbal*

2. **VARSHA GANGADHAR BANGERA**

Signature with date

Shifana
30/6/2022

Varsha
07/07/2022

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, SURATHKAL, MANGALORE-574146

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled "**SMART HELMET FOR MINING WORKERS**" is a bonafide work carried out by *Mr. Abhay Kamath, Mr. Akash J Bangera,* and *Mr. Ashok Kumar* bearing the USN *ISU18CS001, ISU18CS002,* and *ISU18CS005* in the partial fulfilment for the award of Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science and Engineering of the Srinivas University Institute of Engineering and Technology during the year 2021-2022. It is certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the department library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said-degree.

Name & Signature of the Guide

Ms. Swarna H R

Name & Signature of the H.O.D

Mrs. Shifana Begum

Signature of the Dean

Dr. Thomas Pinto
Dean, SUIET, Mukka

External Viva

Name of the Examiners

1. Nagaraj H H

2. VARSHA G B

Signature with date

Shifana Begum
29/6/2022

Varsha G B
07/07/2022

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, SURATHKAL, MANGALORE-574146

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled "**Automatic Vehicle Accident detection and Enhanced Rescue Management system**" is a bonafide work carried out by **Mr. Azhan Abdul Samad Khan, Mr. Poojary Prajnesh Jayanandan, Mr. Preetham U Nayak** bearing the **ISU18CS006, ISU18CS030, ISU18CS032** in the partial fulfilment for the award of Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science and Engineering of the Srinivas University Institute of Engineering and Technology during the year 2021-2022. It is certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the department library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

Mrs. Shifana Begum
(Guide and H.O.D, SUIET, Mukka)

Dr. Thomas Pinto
(Dean, SUIET, Mukka)

External Viva

Name of the Examiners

Signature with date

1. Nagaraj Athibad

2. VARSHA G B

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, SURATHKAL, MANGALORE-574 146

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled "**FACE MASK ETIQUETTE DETECTION SYSTEM FOR STORE OWNERS AND SHOPPERS**" is a bonafide work carried out by *Mr. K Gautham Kamath, Mr. Mishal Ramesh Salian, Mr. Rakshith, Mr. Swasthik* bearing the USN *1SU18CS013, 1SU18CS021, 1SU18CS035, 1SU18CS047* in the partial fulfillment for the award of Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science and Engineering of the Srinivas University- Institute of Engineering and Technology during the year 2021-2022. It is certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the department library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

Name & Signature of the Guide

Dr. D Veerabhadra Babu

Name & Signature of the H.O.D

Mrs. Shifana Begum

Signature of the Dean

Dr. Thomas Pinto

Dean, SUIET, Mukka

External Viva

Name of the Examiners

VARSHA G B

Signature with date

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, SURATHKAL, MANGALORE-574 146

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled "**ENHANCED METHOD TO ATTAIN QOS USING BRUIT PROTOCOL**" is a bonafide work carried out by *Ms. Akshatha B Yaji, Ms. Hapsa Umaira, Mr. Sambram Alva, Mr. K U Shameel* bearing the USNs *ISU18CS003, ISU18CS010, ISU18CS037, ISU19CS701* in the partial fulfillment for the award of **Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science and Engineering** of the **Srinivas University- Institute of Engineering and Technology** during the year **2021-2022**. It is certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the department library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

Name & Signature of the Gurde & HoD
Mrs. Shifana Begum

Signature of the Dean

Dr. Thomas Pinto

Dean, SUIET, Mukka

External Viva

Name of the Examiners

1.

2. VARSHA G B

Signature with date

01/07/2022

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, MANGALORE-574146

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled "*AN AI AND ML BASED APPROACH ON HANDWRITING TEXT RECOGNITION USING OCR*" is a bonafide work carried out by *Ms. Maithri, Ms. Risha Queeni Tellis, Ms. Shruthika, Ms. Vaishnavi B* bearing the *ISU18CS018, ISU18CS036, ISU18CS041, ISU18CS051* in the partial fulfilment for the award of **Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science and Engineering** of the Srinivas University Institute of Engineering and Technology during the year **2021-2022**. It is certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the department library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

30/06/2022

Name & Signature of the Guide

Ms. Swarna H R

30/6/2022

Name & Signature of the H.O.D

Mrs. Shifana Begum

30/6/22

Signature of the Dean

Dr. Thomas Pinto
Dean, SUIET, Mukka

External Viva

Name of the Examiners

Signature with date

1.

2. **VARSHA G B**

01/07/2022

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, SURATHKAL, MANGALURU-574146

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled "*An Improved Smart System for Smart Waste Management Using Internet of Things*" is a bonafide work carried out by *Mr. Amardeep Ghogare, Ms. Nayak Varsha Satish, Ms. Nikhitha, Mr. Satwik I Naik* bearing the USN *ISU18CS004, ISU18CS026, ISU18CS028, ISU18CS039* in the partial fulfilment for the award of **Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science and Engineering** of the **Srinivas University Institute of Engineering and Technology** during the year **2021-2022**. It is certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the department library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

Akhilraj V. Gadagkar
29/06/2022

Name & Signature of the Guide

Mr. Akhilraj V. Gadagkar

Shifana
29/6/2022

Name & Signature of the H.O.D

Mrs. Shifana Begum

Thomas Pinto
29/6/22

Signature of the Dean

Dr. Thomas Pinto
Dean, SUIET, Mukka

External Viva

Name of the Examiners

Signature with date

1. *Nagaraj Hebbar*

Nagaraj Hebbar

2. *VARSHA G B*

Varsha
07/07/2022

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, SURATHKAL, MANGALORE-574146

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled "**AUTOMATIC FACE DETECTION AND RECOGNITION FOR ATTENDANCE MANAGEMENT**" is a bonafide work carried out by *Ms. Kusuma D R, Mr. Pradeep Maleppagol, Mr. Manoj Kammar, and Mr. Vishal Hegde* bearing the USN *ISU18CS017, ISU18CS019, ISU18CS020 and ISU18CS054* in the partial fulfilment for the award of **Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science and Engineering** of the **Srinivas University Institute of Engineering and Technology** during the year **2021-2022**. It is certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the department library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

Name & Signature of the Guide
Ms. Dyanila Neeta Ferrao

Name & Signature of the H.O.D
Mrs. Shifana Begum

Signature of the Dean
Dr. Thomas Pinto
Dean, SUIET, Mukka

External Viva

Name of the Examiners

Signature with date

1. RESHMA B

08/07/2022

VARSHA G B

02/07/2022

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, SURATHKAL, MANGALURU-574146

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled "**Effective Monitoring and Reporting Method to defend the False Data Injection Attacks using EMAS Mechanisms**" is a bonafide work carried out by *Ms. Fathima Nawabi, Ms. Husaiba Hyder, Ms. Kaushika Shetty, and Ms. Sahana Sharief* bearing the *USN ISU18CS009, ISU18CS012, ISU18CS014, ISU18CS055* in the partial fulfilment for the award of **Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science and Engineering** of the **Srinivas University Institute of Engineering and Technology** during the year **2021-2022**. It is certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the department library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of the project work prescribed for the said degree.

Akhilraj V. Gadagkar
29/06/2022

Name & Signature of the Guide

Mr Akhilraj V. Gadagkar

Shifana
29/6/2022

Name & Signature of the H.O.D

Mrs. Shifana Begum

Thomas Pinto
29/6/22

Signature of the Dean

Dr. Thomas Pinto
Dean, SUIET, Mukka

External Viva

Name of the Examiners

1. RESHMA.B

2. VARSHA G B

Signature with date

Reshma
08/07/2022

Varsha
08/07/2022

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, SURATHKAL, MANGALORE-574146

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled "*A System to Detect the Mango Leaf Disease*" is a bonafide work carried out by *Ms. Kshema, Mr. Primus J Dcruz, Mr. Siddhidh Devadiga, Ms. Vineetha* bearing the *ISU18CS016, ISU18CS033, ISU18CS042, ISU18CS053* in the partial fulfillment for the award of **Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science and Engineering** of the Srinivas University Institute of Engineering and Technology during the year **2021-2022**. It is certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the department library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

Name & Signature of the Guide

Mr. Veeranna Kotagi

Name & Signature of the H.O.D

Mrs. Shifana Begum

Signature of the Dean

Dr. Thomas Pinto
Dean, SUIET, Mukka

External Viva

Name of the Examiners

1. RESHMA B

2. VARSHA G.B

Signature with date

08/07/2022

08/07/2022